

INTERINTEGRATION OF MAGNETIC RESONANCE TOMOGRAPHY AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Introduction. Currently, the application of artificial intelligence technologies in the field of medicine is developing rapidly. In particular, the use of AI algorithms in radiology and medical imaging methods allows to increase the accuracy of diagnosis, speed up the process and reduce human error. This study is devoted to the integration process of magnetic resonance imaging and artificial intelligence.

The Importance of MRI and SI Integration. MRI is a high-tech imaging technique designed to visualize human anatomy and physiological processes, and the role of artificial intelligence in its development is increasing. With the help of SI:

- The process of processing MRI images is accelerated;
- Diagnostic results are more accurate;
- The workload of radiologists is reduced;
- The ability to automatically distinguish pathological processes through images becomes possible.

The role of artificial intelligence in MRI image processing. Images generated during MRI examinations are stored in DICOM format. AI algorithms allow for automatic processing of these images and identification of pathologies. AI technologies serve as an effective tool for image segmentation, detection and analysis of pathological changes. This method is especially important in the diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases (Alzheimer's, Parkinson's) and oncological diseases.

Advantages of SI-based MRI image analysis

1. Speed – In traditional diagnostics, analysis can take 15-90 minutes, while SI reduces this process to 5-10 minutes.
2. Accuracy – Errors due to the human factor are reduced.
3. Automation – Differential diagnosis of images is facilitated using SI algorithms.
4. Flexibility – Using MRI images, it is possible to detect and dynamically monitor various diseases.

Technological solutions for MRI and SI integration. SI software improves MRI diagnostics by integrating with applications such as RadiAnt DICOM Viewer. Using the Python programming language, it is possible to add the SI menu to the software interface. In this case:

- SI and DICOM images are interconnected via API;
- Images are processed using SI algorithms;
- The results obtained help doctors make diagnostic decisions.

Conclusion. The mutual integration of magnetic resonance imaging and artificial intelligence plays an important role in improving the quality of medical diagnostics, ensuring the accuracy of results, and optimizing the workflow of doctors. With the help of SI, the efficiency of MRI examinations increases and the diagnosis process is automated, creating new opportunities in the healthcare system.